

A Study On Job Satisfaction Of Employees In It Sector In Chennai

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ABSTRACT

Job Satisfaction is the extent to which an employee feels his or her measure of contentedness with their job such as nature of job, supervision and improvement opportunities etc...The IT industry comprises of software development, consultancies, software management, online services and business process outsourcing (BPO) and is an industry undergoing rapid advancement thereby changing the Indian business community. The biggest benefit that IT industries provide are that of employment to an extent that currently India has more software developers in the world than any country. Employees want to earn good living by avoiding excess amount of stress and to gain benefits like quality of life and social status. People prefer profession in IT sectors because they want to use their skills and capabilities. Higher satisfaction levels among the employees result in improvement of productivity and thereby increase in revenue. Most IT companies have started recognizing the effect of satisfaction and are increasing their focus on HR issues and employee motivational activities.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Information Technology, Productivity, Revenue, Motivational Factors.

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is the main factor for each and every employee to work for their motive to develop intellectual and it improves the employee's interest for development of individual and corporate skills for self and company's betterment. In this buzzing world, every industry is grooming their resources to embrace higher technology and to enhance communication skills to reach to all levels. This can make each and every person to develop their interest for achievement of job. For achieving their own ideas and skills they have to get satisfaction during performance of their job. As of 2018, Chennai has become the second-largest exporter of IT and BPO services in the country and has an IT corridor that has been labeled as Asia's largest IT park when it was built. A lot of the IT field's leading companies have their offices set up here, with some of them making Chennai their largest base.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study overall work environment in IT industries in Chennai.
- To analyze the various employee aspects & external factors which affecting job satisfaction and their effect on different income groups of employees.
- To provide suggestions for improvement of job satisfaction levels among employees.

Sources of Data

The survey was collected from two sources of data viz.,

1. Primary data
2. Secondary data

In this study we have taken both primary and secondary data. The primary data have been collected through a well constructed Questionnaire having thirty eight questions. Data have been collected from 77 respondents. The data which already exists or published by somebody else or any organization or Government data collected and presented. We have collected the secondary data through, Magazines, News Papers, books, Journals, Websites and other already published data.

Tools and techniques

The following tools and techniques have been used to present the data simple and clear. In this study statistical tool, simple percentage method, F- Test, Chi-Square test, Garrett Ranking techniques have been applied.

S No	Demographic Factors	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	42	54.54
		Female	35	45.46
2	Qualification	Professional	18	23.38
		Degree Holder	31	40.26
		Post Graduate	20	25.97
		Diploma Holder	8	10.39
3	Age Group	21-30 Years	30	38.96
		31-40 Years	22	28.57
		41-50 Years	13	16.88
		Above 50 Years	12	15.58
4	Experience Level	Less than 6 months	7	9.09
		6 months – 2 years	18	23.37
		2 – 5 Yrs	25	32.46
		More than 5 years	27	35.06
5	Income Group	Up to Rs.20,000	9	11.68
		Rs.20,001 to Rs.30,000	23	29.87
		Rs.30,001 to 40,000	29	35.06
		Above Rs.40,000	19	23.37

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**Table.1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents**

Source: Computed Primary data

Table 5.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. There are 54 percent of male respondents and 45 percent of female respondents who have participated in the survey. Majority of respondents 39 percent are in age group of 21-30 years, 29 percent of respondents are between 31-40 years, 17 percent of respondents between 41-50 years and 15 percent of respondents are more than 50 years. On educational qualification, 40 percent of respondents are Degree holders, 26 percent are post graduates while a similar 23.5 percent are Professional degree holders and only a meager 10 percent are Diploma holders. The above table reveals that 11 percent of respondents come under income group up to Rs.20000, 30 percent of respondents between Rs.20000-30000, 35 percent of respondents between Rs.30000-40000 and 23 percent of respondents above Rs.40000. According to this table 9 percent of employees are having experience of less than 6 months, 23 percent of respondents are having experience of 6 months to 1 year, 32 percent of respondents have experience between 2- 5 years while 35 percent are having more than 5 years of experience level.

Table .2 Motivational factors for better performance

Sl. No.	Prominent features	Income group			Total	F-Statistics
		Low	Middle	High		
1	New Challenges	3.57	3.20	3.08	3.26	.367
2	Implementation of ideas	2.57	3.00	3.69	3.12	.005
3	Flexible Work Timings	3.52	3.20	3.08	3.25	.446
4	Rewards, Incentives, etc.,	3.05	2.93	3.23	3.06	.699
5	Pursuing higher studies	3.10	2.83	3.15	3.01	.579

Source: Computed Primary Data

The above table summates that among various motivational factors for better performance New Challenges is the most prominent feature for IT employees among all income groups with an overall mean of 3.26. And also low and middle income group respondents' have rated 3.57 and 3.20 for new challenges. Implementation of ideas scored high as motivation with a mean of 3.69 across high income group. New challenges and

flexible work timings are high among middle income groups as motivational factors for employees of IT sector with mean value of 3.20. New challenges have scored high among low income groups with a mean score of 3.57.

H₀₁ : There is no significant difference among different income group and motivation factors for better performance

The above hypothesis has been tested in the light one way ANOVA. The results are given in table no.5.3. It can be concluded from the above table that framed null hypothesis has been rejected in case of implementation of ideas. In case of new challenges, flexible work timings, rewards & incentives and pursuing higher studies the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus it is concluded that there is a significant difference among income group people on the motivation for better performance from flexible work timings, rewards & incentives and pursuing higher studies. Based on the mean score and F-test results the employees still need recognition for creativity and personal growth and involvement & responsibility among employees.

Table .3 Employee Aspects affecting job satisfaction

SI No	Aspects	Income Group			Mean score	χ^2
		Low	Middle	High		
1	Provision of Training	3.35	3.48	3.07	3.29	.814
2	Performance monitoring	3.58	3.22	3.14	3.31	.138
3	Teamwork	3.46	3.35	3.25	3.35	.830
4	Employee Participation	3.31	3.22	3.00	3.17	.468
5	Skill Set development	3.46	3.26	3.32	3.35	.339

Source: Computed Primary Data

Table 5.4 summates that employee aspects affecting job satisfaction in IT sector by the various income group people. Among low income group Performance monitoring has scored the mean value of 3.58. In the middle income group Provision of training has scored with a mean score of 3.48. Among high income group Skill Set development has got highest mean score of 3.32. It is concluded that teamwork and Skill Set development has provided

high score 3.35 in case of employee aspects towards job satisfaction among all income groups.

H ₀ 1	:	There is no relationship between different income group and employee aspects affecting job satisfaction
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The above hypothesis has been tested in the chi square test. The results are given in table no.4.29. It can be concluded from the above table that framed null hypothesis has been rejected in case of Provision of Training, teamwork and employee participation and in the case of Performance monitoring the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus there is a significant difference among income group people on the provision of training, teamwork and employee participation.

Table .4 Extrinsic factors affecting job satisfaction

Sl. No.	Factors	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted Average	Rank
1.	Monetary benefits	7670	76.23	5
2.	Atmosphere of Work	8131	80.01	1
3.	Supervision level	7832	78.02	3
4.	Nature of Job	8025	79.35	2
5.	Management Vision towards employee development	7798	77.90	4
6.	Co-worker relationship	7360	73.05	6
7.	Travel necessity	6854	68.33	7

Source: Computed Primary Data

On the basis of Garrett ranking method, the list of extrinsic factors affecting job satisfaction has been ranked based on respondent observations. Atmosphere of work scored I rank with a weighted average of 80.01 while nature of job scored II rank with average of 79.35. Supervision level scored III rank with a weighted average of 78.02, Management vision towards employee development scored IV rank, Monetary benefits scored V rank, Co-worker relationship scored

VI rank while travel necessity scored VII rank. Thus by Garrett ranking method atmosphere of work among IT employees plays a major role in extrinsic factors towards job satisfaction.

Findings of the Study

- 54 percent of respondents are male.
- 40 percent of respondents are degree holders
- 38 percent of employees are in age group of 21-30 yrs.
- 35 percent of employees are having experience for more than 5 yrs.
- 35 percent of employees are come under income group of Rs.30000 to Rs.40000.
- Using F-Test, there is no significant difference among different income group and motivation factors for better performance
- By Chi-square test, there is no relationship between different income group and employee aspects affecting job satisfaction
- On the basis of Garrett ranking method, atmosphere of work scored I rank with a weighted average of 80.01

Suggestions

- New Challenges is the most prominent feature for all IT employees among all income groups.
- There is a significant difference among income group people on the motivation for better performance from flexible work timings, rewards & incentives and pursuing higher studies.
- Teamwork and Skill Set development are the employee aspects that have a great impact towards job satisfaction among all income groups.
- There is a significant difference among income group people on the provision of training, teamwork and employee participation.
- Atmosphere of work among IT employees plays a major role in extrinsic factors towards job satisfaction.

CONCLUSIONS

As the technology grows, there is a rapid improvement in all type of communication which reaches all categories of people. This can be done through changes in IT sector. In this study, employees in IT sector facing some motivational factors and also employee aspects which affects job satisfaction. This can be changed by giving new challenges and ideas to employees and also to make through teamwork. By providing some monetary benefits and a good relationship among employees, they can maintain job satisfaction for all. Suggestions to be made to IT

companies for better monitoring of new challenges, improvement of team work and skill set development among employees and creating a cordial atmosphere for work can be looked into to maintain a better employee satisfaction.

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